

The Times, Are They A-Changin'? Unmuddling the Politics of Time in the MENA

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Claims of generational differences seem to be everywhere in qualitative and ethnographic studies of the Middle East nowadays. Here are several examples. Youssef El Chazli argues that participation in mass protests during the 2010-11 Arab Uprisings had a range of life-altering effects on young Egyptians' friendship networks, family lives, and careers (El Chazli 2020). Revolutions have afterlives. Marsin Alshamary found that many young Iraqis today, disillusioned with the corruption and sectarianism of their country's parliamentary democracy, express nostalgia for the strongman Ba'athist era (Alshamary 2018). Authoritarian pasts have afterlives too, even – or especially – among those who never experienced them. In a similar vein, policies are sometimes based on assumed differences among generations. Supporters of the Iran nuclear deal, for example, justified its controversial 10 to 15-year sunset clauses by noting that a new generation of Iranian political and clerical leaders will – over that time – replace those of the generation that carried out the 1979 revolution (e.g., Sick 2015). After the lives of The Revolution, so to speak.

Over the past 25 years, such generational analyses of the MENA seem to have become increasingly common. I see several

reasons for this trend. The first is the broad and important puzzle of why so many educated youth turned to Islamism in the 1980s and early 1990s. Although Carrie Rosefsky Wickham's seminal book on Islamic activism is most frequently cited for documenting Egypt's parallel Islamic sector, her core argument rests on a cohort analysis (Rosefsky Wickham 2002). She argues that the Islamic movement's ideological outreach resonated with the life experiences of an educated and underemployed generation of Egyptians, allowing the movement to capture their hearts and minds and eventually getting them to move from low-risk to higher-risk forms of activism. The second reason for the rise of generational analyses is the widespread belief that the spread of new technologies in the region in the late 1990s and early 2000s – satellite television and internet access – undermined state control over information and shaped new public spheres (e.g., Lynch 2006). Finally, a decade of seemingly "momentous events" from 2001 to 2011 – the attacks of September 11th, the U.S.-led invasion of Iraq, the Arab Uprisings – reverberated through the MENA and were experienced by its publics in complex ways. It is widely assumed – although rarely examined empirically – that this cascade of upheavals shaped the formative years of a generation.

Yet, despite this broad interest in generational change and numerous rich ethnographies that speak to it, I posit that we still know little – with any degree of confidence – about the politics of time and if and how social generations differ from one another in the MENA. Qualitative scholars, including those mentioned above, have made bold and important claims. But future qualitative research could benefit by learning from conceptual work done by quantitative scholars on age-period-cohort effects. Quantitative scholars have had to pay close attention to conceptually differentiating between age, period, and cohort (APC) effects because of a particular statistical challenge related to deriving unique estimators for all three effects (when the *period* in which an individual is observed minus the individual's *age* equals the individual's birth year, with the latter fully determining *cohort*). It is far from clear how useful the particular strategies that quantitative scholars have developed to overcome this identification challenge might be for qualitative work, but they offer clear and consistent concepts that can travel across methodological traditions. I am not suggesting that qualitative scholars should change their feathers and become experts in R. Far from it. I merely am arguing that qualitative work on time and “generations” (broadly defined) would benefit from clearer conceptualizations and that quantitative APC scholarship offers useful legwork in this regard.

APC analysis differentiates between three possible effects of time. The first is age or life-cycle effects, linked to the social processes of aging. The second is period effects, which are external factors that affect all age groups at a particular time (e.g., wars, economic crises). The third is cohort effects – differences among age-groups – which come in two flavors. Cohort effects have tradition-

ally been understood as the sum of all the unique life experiences and exposures of a cohort from birth (a sort of structural factor). But a cohort effect can also be conceptualized as an event that is experienced differently by age-cohorts (a heterogeneous period or treatment effect). Is watching the current war in Gaza having roughly the same effect on Arabs of all ages (a period effect)? Or, perhaps, is it fueling greater rage among younger Arabs – those aged 15 to 21 – because they are still in their “formative years” (a type of cohort effect)? And how would we know?

A preliminary set of best practices for research on generations – be it qualitative, quantitative, formal theory, experimental, or any flavor of “mixed method” research – might begin by being explicit about 1) the *purported* change or difference (e.g., period or cohort) being posited; 2) why that difference, and why that specific difference instead of another (i.e., precise specification of a mechanism); and 3) whether the change or difference is being either assumed or hypothesized and then evaluated. One area in which much quantitative APC analysis falls short is in the development of refined theory, causal stories that are coherent, non-contradictory, and non-tautological. Some would say this is a strength of qualitative research: identifying new theories and addressing questions of process. Refined theories of time developed by qualitative-leaning researchers might, over time, percolate back to influence quantitative-leaning APC analyses.

How did the Arab Uprisings affect participants? If scholars focus only on participants of a certain age group – such as youth – it is difficult to know if changes in their lives over time are attributable to their participation in the uprisings or to the fact that they are growing older. Further, it is impossible to

know if the uprisings affected younger participants differently than older ones without explicit comparison. Many Arab youth today might yearn for the stability, opportunities, and services that they think were available under strongmen decades ago, but do older generations of Arabs – including those who remember those eras – feel a similar nostalgia? Perhaps we are witnessing a general “period” of nostalgia for strongmen, not the formation of a distinct generation. Or – recalling Rosefsky Wickham’s analysis of Egyptian youth in the 1980s and early 1990s – maybe there is a pattern in the region of young people being jealous of opportunities they believe earlier generations had (a type of “age” effect). How and why should we expect the generation of Iranian leaders from the 1979 revolution to differ from the generation of Iranian leaders that emerged under the subsequent Islamic Republic? These are all important questions for understanding the MENA today. Existing conceptual work by APC researchers provides a useful framework that can inform and structure qualitative comparisons and ethnographic observations to help answer them. Hopefully the next generation of research on generations will learn from the past. ♦

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